

Fermion Clusters and Bosonic Ripples – The Phoenix Principle

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Abstract:

By analyzing the coupling constants series and the main equation of the 8T, it is possible to reason for a recursive process between arbitrary variations vanishing into matter, and net variations, which are net curvature of the manifold, causing fermions to cluster at larger and larger scale. It is the recursive process governing the large-scale formations on the Einstein manifold, and supported by the coupling constant primordial function, derived in March 2021. The process can be represented by using the variation of the Dirac delta.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.13)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.14)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.15)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.16)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.17)$$

Equations (1.16) (1.17) are the ones that presenting the recursive dance of everything. Arbitrary variations of the manifold vanish into matter. Net variations are ripples of the manifold, appear randomly causing the fermions to cluster. The cluster than again is subject to random net curvature causing larger scale clustering and the process goes on and on. Equation (1.17) represent only the photon but it is true regarding any additional element in the series. as they are not yet found there isn't a known symbol to represent them. The following recursive process was represented in the 8-theory thesis in the form of the delta function presented by Dirac:

$$\delta g \neq 0 \quad at \quad t = Q(t) \quad (1.18)$$

$$\delta g = 0 \quad at \quad t = Q(t + \Delta t) \quad (1.19)$$

Representing arbitrary variations vanishing into matter. In addition, the following two terms, net curvature propagating from matter causing a clustering at larger scale:

$$\delta g = 0 \quad at \quad t = Q(t + \Delta t) \quad (1.19)$$

$$\delta g \neq 0 \quad at \quad t_2 = Q(t + \Delta t + \Delta t) \quad (1.191)$$

Similar to rebirth of the phoenix, so shall be called the phoenix principle. An endless chain of rebirths. A tale of between even amount of arbitrary variations and prime amount (or one) net variations, which are curvature on the manifold. The dance of everything, the tale of the phoenix – now verified.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)